

Research Article

Phytochemical and Antibacterial Activity of *Carica papaya* Root Extract on Some Selected Pathogens**¹Kashari, O., ¹Osesua, B.A., ¹Danjumma, B.J. and ²Udeme, A.M****¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, College of Science and Technology Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, BirninKebbi, Kebbi State Nigeria****²Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe, Bayelsa State. Corresponding author:**

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Abstract

The phytochemical and antibacterial activity of *Carica papaya* root extracts was carried out on some selected pathogens. The *Carica papaya* root was extracted using water and ethanol as solvents for extraction and the phytochemical screening carried out for the *Carica papaya* root extracts revealed the presence of some bioactive compounds such as Flavonoids, Tannins, Saponins, Alkaloids, Steroids and Terpenes while free anthraquinones, glycosides and carbohydrate were absent in both the water and ethanol extract of *Carica papaya*. The test organisms (*Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) were clinical isolates obtained from Federal Medical Centre, BirninKebbi. The bacteria susceptibility test was carried out using Agar "well" diffusion method. The effect of the *Carica papaya* root of both water and ethanol extracts was determined using various concentrates (10mg/ml, 20mg/ml, 30mg/ml and 40mg/ml respectively) of the extracts. The water extract has good activity of 17.0mm zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* while the ethanol extract has an activity of 18.0mm of inhibition against *Salmonella typhi* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The differences in the observed activity may be due to the varying degrees of solubility of the active constituents in the solvent used. This suggests that ethanol may have the stronger extraction capacity for the bioactive compounds and those that want to utilize *Carica papaya* root for the development of traditional medicines to create a new way to treat many incurable diseases may use ethanol as solvent for extraction. However, toxicological studies should be carried out to determine the level of toxic substances and how it can be reduced, the isolated compounds should be separated, purified and characterized and there is also need for further research in this area so as to serve as confirmation.

Key words: bioactive, susceptibility, "well", inhibition, varying, diffusion

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Introduction

Natural products are compounds that originate from microbes/plants or animal sources (Charles, 2005). As chemical compounds, natural products include such classes of compounds as terpenoids, polypeptides, amino acid, protein, carbohydrates, lipids, nucleic acids (e.g. ribonucleic acid (RNA) and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and so forth. Natural products are generally classified into two, the primary metabolites e.g. cellulose and the secondary metabolites e.g. alkaloids, based on their activity within the host organism, since there is no valid distinction based on structure or biochemistry (Rodney et al, 2000).

The primary metabolites are the compounds participating in nutrition and essential metabolic processes in the plant while secondary metabolites are those influencing ecological interactions between the plant and its environment (Rodney et al, 2000). However, the importance of plants cannot be over-emphasized over a long period of time; plants have been used by mankind for many different purposes such as food, shelter, and medicine. Plants have also been used by traditional healers in the treatment of various diseases (Uwumanrongie, et al, 2007).

Phytochemistry is the scientific discipline used to describe medicinal plant consisting of the study of how to extract, concentrate, analyze, standardize and preserve herbal product. Plant-derived substances have recently become of great interest due to their versatile applications. Medicinal plants are the richest bio-resources of drugs of traditional system of modern medicine and chemical entities for synthetic drugs.

Significance of The Research

Carica papaya is a very important perennial herb commonly used in the treatment of malaria, wound infection of bacteria origin and typhoid fever worldwide and scientists have endoured this ancient practice finding it effective in the treatment of diseases, as reported in many literatures, even though environmental conditions, soil texture and genetic variation exert a significant influence on the variation of chemical constituents of the plant (Hassan and Umar, 2004). It is important to determine the chemical constituent of the plant within each local environment. However, this research is with the view to determine the phytochemical and antibacterial activity of *Carica papaya* root.

This research work is aimed at determining the phytochemical and antibacterial activity of *Carica papaya* root on some selected pathogens through the following objectives.

- To extract *Carica papaya* root with water and ethanol.
- To determine the phytochemical compounds present in the extract.
- To determine the antibacterial activity of the extracts on the test organisms.

Botany of The Plant

Carica papaya (belongs to the family called caricaceae, commonly known as pawpaw (English), Gwanda (Hausa), Ibepe (Yoruba) or Okroegbe (Igbo). (Gbile and Solade, 2002). *Carica papaya* is a native to the tropic of the Americans, and was first cultivated in Mexico several centuries before the emergence of the Mesoamerican classical civilization. The *Carica papaya* is a large tree-like plant with a single stem growing from 5 to 10 meters high with spirally arranged leave contained to the long of the trunk (Suresh *et al*, 2008).

Uses of the plant

Besides the fruits of *Carica papaya* being edible, they have been reported along with the roots, stem bark and leaves to be of medicinal value. The latex from the leaves have been used for the treatment of infections of bacterial origin (Fajimiet *al.*, 2001). It is also marketed in tablet form to remedy digestive problems. Women in India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sri-Lanka, and other countries have been using it for a long time as a remedy for contraceptive and abortion. The root extract may be used for the treatment of gastroenteritis, urethritis, typhoid fever and wound infection, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Psidium guajava* and discovered that *Carica papaya* possessed higher antimicrobial activity among the plant extract.

Ethnopharmacological Research

The study of plants used in traditional medicine requires the effective integration of information on chemical composition of extracts, pharmacological activities or isolated compounds, as well as indigenous knowledge of traditional healers. The acquisition of ethnobotanical information remains an empirical aspect in any such study (Soejarto, 2005). The process of isolating and identifying lead compounds from a complex mixture requires a number of specific resources, including comprehensive knowledge, specialized equipment and skill. The urgency of the discovery of new agents is a result of impenetrable factors that come into play, including the emergence of new killer diseases, known antimicrobial drug-resistance, the inefficiency of synthetic drug

discovery and the high cost of bringing to market a single drug. A shift towards natural product research which is further driven by remarkable advances in plant extract technology, biotechnology and analytical chemistry, is therefore inevitable (Paraskeva, 2008).

There is a great need and ethical obligation to accurately document investigative findings on plants used for health purposes. This will additionally aid in the efficient preservation and conservation of traditional knowledge, thereby preventing the further disappearance of indigenous systems of medicine, which may potentially benefit society in general (Phillipson, 2001).

Plants used in traditional medicines are more likely to have pharmacologically active compounds compared to a random selection of plant materials. The ethnomedicine information gathered from the traditional medicine can be used to drive research towards drug development (Nabulega, 2010). One of the native Nigerian plants of interest is *Carica papaya*. Based on the ethnomedicine information, *Carica papaya* has been deemed desirable for further studies. In the current study, the root of *Caricapapaya* has been taken for phytochemical and antibacterial activities against some selected organisms.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Fresh sample of *Carica papaya* root was collected from Fadama area of Kebbi State, the fresh roots were harvested and properly washed in tap running water to remove soil particles and dust (Mishraet *al.*, 2012). The roots were cut into smaller pieces and air dried for fourteen days and ground into powdered form with a wooden mortar and pestle.

Extraction of Plant Materials

Ten grams of the powdered sample were measured using weighing balance and it was poured in 100ml of distilled water. The same procedure was repeated for 20g, 30g and 40g to obtain a varying concentration of 10mg/ml, 20mg/ml, 30mg/ml and 40mg/ml respectively. 10g of the powdered root of *Carica papaya* was soaked in 100ml of ethanol for 24 hours and the mixture was shaken after some interval of time, the mixture was filtered and concentrated using water bath to obtain a concentration of

10mg/ml of the ethanol extract, the same procedure was repeated for 20g, 30g and 40g to obtain varying concentrations of 30mg/ml and 40mg/ml respectively. The samples were preserved in the refrigerator.

Media Preparation

The media used in this research work were prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction. The media used were nutrient broth and nutrient agar.

Test Organisms

The microorganisms used in this research work were *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. These are all clinical isolates obtained from Federal Medical Centre BirninKebbi, Kebbi State. The test organisms were inoculated in nutrient broth contained in 100ml conical flask and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and was sub-cultured into nutrient agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to obtain a pure culture.

Determination of Morphological Characteristics

From the colonies that developed on nutrient agar, a smear was made with a glass-slide using a sterile wire loop that was dried and heat fixed. The smear was flooded with crystal violet solution for 30 seconds and washed, this was later poured out and covered with lugols iodine for 30-60 seconds and was washed off and decolourized with acid alcohol. The smear was counter stained with safranin solution for 60 seconds, followed by rinsing with distilled water. This was then allowed to air dry before viewing under the microscope using oil immersion objectives (x 100) (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008)

Biochemical Test

The following biochemical tests (catalase, coagulase, citrate, motility, indole, urease, triple sugar iron, methyl red, spore detection and vogesproskauer test) were carried out as described in Oyeleke and Manga, 2008, to identify the organisms to the species level.

Phytochemical Screening

The followings are some phytochemical screening test carried out. This research work is in accordance to standard described by (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Test for Alkaloid: 0.5g of the extract was stirred with 5cm³ of 10.1% aqueous hydrochloric acid on a steam bath. The 1cm³ of the filtrate was treated separately with

few drops of Dangedorff's reagent. Mayer's reagent and Wangers reagent, a deep brown creamy precipitate indicates a positive test.

Test for Flavonoids: One millimeter (1ml) of the extract was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution which disappeared on addition of hydrochloric acid, indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Tannins (Ferric Chloride Test): A portion of water extract diluted with distilled water in a ratio of 1:4 and a few drops of 10% ferric chloride solution was added, blue or green colour indicated the presence of Tannins.

Test for Glycosides: (Keller - Killani Test) 0.5g of each extract was dissolved in 3cm of 3.5cm³ FeCl₃, in glacial acetic acid and left for minutes. 1.5cm of H₂SO₄ was pipette into it in order to min down the side of the test tube. A positive test will serve as a clear interphase with a blue layer.

Test for Saponins: 10ml of distilled water was added into 0.5ml of extract in a test tube. The content was shaken vigorously with the test tube for (two) minutes. The presence of fronting or bubbling will indicate the presence of saponins.

Test for Steroid: Five (5) drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added into 1ml of the extract. A reddish brown colour indicates the presence of steroid.

Test for Carbohydrate: (General Metabolism): A few drops of Molisch Reagent was added into 2cm³ of the water extract, and 1.5cm of sulphuric acid was added and allowed to form a lower layer purple ring at the interface of the liquids indicate the presence of carbohydrate.

Test for Anthraquinones (Borntrager's Test): 0.5g of the extract was taken in a different test tube and 10mls of chloroform was added and then shaken for 5 minutes. The extract was shaken again. A bright pink coloured in the aqueous layer indicate the presence of Anthraquinone.

Test for Terpenes (LieberBurhad Test): The first portion of the chloroform solution from the extract mixed with 1ml of acetic anhydride and 1ml concentrated sulphuric acid down the wall of the test tubes was added to form a layer underneath, the formation of reddish colour indicates the presence of terpenes.

Preparation of Test Medium

The test medium (nutrient agar) was prepared using standard procedures described in Oyeleke and Manga (2008). A sterile syringe was obtained and cut from the edge, using a sterile razor blade, the syringe (12mm) in diameter was used to dig a "well" the varying concentrations of the *Carica papaya* extracts were then used to fill the "wells". After inoculating the test bacteria on each of the plates, they were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Results and DiscussionsTable 1: **Phytochemical Analysis of *Carica papaya* root**

Component Extract	Level of their Presence	
	WE	EE
Flavonoids	++	+
Tannins	+	+
Saponins	++	+
Alkaloids	+	+
Steroids	++	+
Anthraquinones	-	-
Glycosides	-	-
Terpenes	++	++
Carbohydrate	-	-

Keys:

++	=	Present
+	=	Slight present
-	=	Absent
WE	=	Water extract
EE	=	Ethanol extract

Table 2: Shows the mean zone of inhibition of *Carica papaya* water extract against the test organisms.

Organisms	Zone of Inhibition in (mm) per mg/ml Concentrations			
	10	20	30	40
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	4.0	6.0	6.0	0.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	4.0	6.0	8.0	12.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	4.0	6.0	12.0	8.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	4.0	6.0	10.0	14.0

Table 3: Shows the mean zone of inhibition of *Carica papaya* ethanol extract against the test organisms.

Organisms	Zone of Inhibition in (mm) per mg/ml Concentrations			
	10	20	30	40
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	0.0	7.0	7.0	8.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	4.0	6.0	9.0	14.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	4.0	8.0	12.0	18.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	0.0	6.0	12.0	18.0

Discussion

The results of the phytochemical analysis of *Carica papaya* root of both water and crude ethanol extracts revealed the presence of some bioactive compounds such as Flavonoids, Tannins, Saponins, Alkaloids, Steroids and Tapenes while free anthraquinones, glycosides and carbohydrate were absent in both the water and crude ethanol extract of *Carica papaya*.

Phytochemicals have been found to inhibit bacteria, fungi, viruses and pests. The presence of phytochemicals in the root of *Carica papaya* may be responsible for the antibacterial activity of the plant (Margorie, 1999), for instance, the presence of tannins in plants extracts which is known to have antibacterial and antifungal properties may

give the chance for traditional practitioners to use it as remedies for fever and headache, convulsions and stomach disorder.

Alkaloids are known to exhibit anesthetics, analgesics and antihelminthic properties and can be used for the treatment of stomach problem. Saponins also have medicinal value because it can be taken orally to lower cholesterol level in the body (Uwumanrongie *et al.*, 2007). Water and ethanol extract of *Carica papaya* root were tested for antibacterial activity to ascertain the traditional practitioners' claims, the results of the antibacterial activity of water extract against the test organisms are presented in Table 2. The result revealed that water extract has good activity of 17.0mm zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*, while the ethanol extract has an activity of 18.0mm of inhibition against *Salmonella typhi* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. A similar result was reported by Adeniyi *et al.* (2011) on *Carica papaya* root ethanol extract. The antibacterial activity of the ethanol extract compared favourably with standard antibiotic tetracycline. The differences in the observed activity may be due to the varying degrees of solubility of the active constituents in the solvent used (Umar *et al.*, 2011). The result obtained is also similar to the one reported by Doughari *et al.* (2007) on the antibacterial studies of *Caricapapaya* root extract. It is likely that the active constituents of the plant were better extracted with ethanol, indicating that ethanol is a better solvent. This result also agreed with the findings of Camarda *et al.* (2007), that high concentrations of antimicrobial substances of the same extract could show appreciable inhibition.

Conclusion

This research work revealed the presence of some bioactive compounds such as Flavonoids, Tannins, Alkaloids, Saponins and Steroids in the root of *Carica papaya* extract. The finding of this research work also showed that ethanol extract were more effective against all the test bacteria than the water extract, which may be due to the better solubility of bioactive compounds in ethanol. This suggests that ethanol may have the stronger extraction capacity for the bioactive compounds and those that want to utilize *Carica papaya* root for the development of traditional medicines to create a new way to treat many incurable diseases may use ethanol as salient for extraction.

This research work revealed that *Carica papaya* root contains many bioactive compounds which may be used for treatment of various diseases, such as typhoid fever and stomach disorder, due to the ability of the plant extract to inhibit all the test organisms.

Therefore, toxicological studies should be carried out to determine the level of toxic substances and how it can be reduced. Isolated compounds should be separated, purified and characterized.

References

Adeniyi O. A and Elizabeth O. T (2011): Comparative Study of antibacterial activities of ethanol extract of the Bark and Seed of *Garcinia Kola* and *Carica papaya*. *African Journal of Biomedical Research* Vol. 14, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Charles, B.S., (2005): *Drug Discovery Handbook*, New Jersey; John Wiley and Sons Inc. Pp 1496-1498.

Camarda, L., Dayto, T., Di-Stefano, V., Pitonzon, R., and Schillaci, D. (2007): Chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of some oelgum resin essential oils from *Boswellia spp.* *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 97:837-844

Doughari, J.H. E.L-Mahmoud, A.M and Manzara, S. (2007): Antibacterial activity of *Tamar indusindica* Linn, *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, retrieve at www.academicjournals.org/ajmr.

Fajimi, A.K, Taiwo, A.A, Ayodeji, H., Adebowale, E.A, Ogundola, F.I. (2001): Therapeutic trials on gastrointestinal helminthes parasites of goat using pawpaw seeds as a dench. Proceedings of the international conference on sustainable crop, livestock production for improvement livelihood and Natural Resources Management, West Africa International Institute of Tropical BA Agriculture retrieve from www.academicjournals.org/ajmr.

Gbile, Z and Solade, M. (2002): *Vernacular Names of Nigerian Plants (Yoruba)* Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan, Molukom Press, Ibadan.

Hassan, L.G and Umar, K.J (2004): Proximate and Mineral Composition of seed and Pulp of African Locust Bean (*Parkia biglobosa*, L), *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 13, 15-29.

Marjorie, M.C (1999): Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clinical Microbiology*, 12 (4), 564-582.

Mishra, G.J, Reddy, M.N and Rana, J.S (2012): Isolation of Flavonoid Constituent from *Launaeaprocumbens* ROX. By preparative HPTLC Method. *Journal of Pharmacy* Vol. 2, Gujarat University, Surat, Gujarat, India.

Nalubega, R. (2010): Antibacterial and Phytochemical properties of selected Poultry Ethnomedicinal Plants in Masaka District, M.Sc. Dissertation Maker ere University, Uganda pp.114.

Oyeleke, S.B. and Manga, B.S. (2008): Essential Laboratory Practical in Microbiology, 1st ed., Tobest Publisher, Minna, pp. 23-68.

Paraskeva, M. (2008): The Pharmacological Activity of Ten Species of Commiphora Indigenous to South Africa, Ph.D Thesis, University of the Wit Watersrand, South Africa, pp. 244.

Phillipson, J.D. (2001): Phytochemistry and Medicinal Plants, *Phytochemistry*, 56, 237-243.

Rodney, C., Toni, M.K and Norman, G.L (2000): Natural Products (Secondary Metabolites), In: Buchanan, B. Gruissem, W. and Jones, R. (eds). *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology of Plants*. Rockville *American Society of Plant Physiologists*, 1250-1251.

Soejarto, O.D (2005): Ethnographic Component and Organism Documentation in an Ethnopharmacology paper. A "Minimum" Standard, *Ethnopharmacology*, 100, 27-29.

Suresh, R., Sudheer, K.S, Christian, L., Carlos, R.S and Ashok, P. (2008): Oil cakes and their Biotechnological Applications - A Review, *Bioresource Technology*, 98, 2000-2009.

Umar, K.J, Hassan, L.G and Garba, H.L (2011): Nutritive Value of Some Indigenous Spices, Cloves and African Black pepper, *Chemclass*, 3, 81-84.

Uwumanrongie, O.H, Obasuyi, O. and Uwumanrongie, G. (2007): Phytochemical Analysis and Antimicrobial Screening of the Root of *Jatrophanjorensis* Ellis and Soraja (Family Euphorbiaceae) *Chemical Technology Journal*, Vol. 3. 111-184.